

Research

Characterization of Ridge Gourd Germplasm

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Abstract : To know about the genetic diversity of 80 accessions of ridge gourd, an experiment was designed in the experimental field of Plant Genetic Resources Centre (PGRC) of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, during the Rabi season of 2017-18. Eighty germplasm of ridge gourd were included in the experiment but out of them only 44 germplasm were germinated and among them finally seeds of 40 collections could be collected for characterization. Wide variations were found in both qualitative and quantitative characters among the germplasm and concerning all the characters, the TT-177, AR-197, ATR-18, AHM-215, AC-338, TT-167, AMA-244, KI-38, N-6, RAI-296, AMA-395, AMA-182, TT-26, RC-155, BD-10281 and BD-10282 germplasm were the promising lines for future breeding programs and other research also. germplasm were found as the promising lines.

Keywords: Ridge gourd, Characterization, Quantitative analysis

Introduction

Ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula*), an important member of the family Cucurbitaceae grown throughout the country, is a fast-growing vine that often requires some support to facilitate its spread. It is a climbing annual grown primarily for its immature fruits which are eaten raw, pickled

or cooked commonly used in soups and curries (Tindall, 1987). The immature fruits which may show morphological differences depending on the cultivar are good sources of vitamin A, B, C and minerals (Morton, 1967; Wills et al., 1984) and has a considerable medicinal importance (Bora *et al.* 2015) such as Vit-C for keeping away colds, Vit-B for good mood and vitality, zinc for strengthening our immune system, iron for anemia, manganese and magnesium for enzyme production and immunity and calcium and phosphorus for strong bones. As fresh ridge gourd contain folates, in the expectant mothers, this folate-rich food may help in reducing the incidences of neural tube defects in the newborns. The seeds are a good source of iron, magnesium, and phosphorous and contain high amounts of essential amino acids such as lysine (Kamel and Blackman, 1982). Its high fiber content helps with healthy digestion and proper functioning of the excretory system. However, seeds of some varieties are bitter due to high levels of bitter steroids like Cucurbitacin B (Watt and Breyer-Brandwijk, 1962). The pure seed oil is tasteless and contains 68 percent of glycerides of oleic and linoleic acids, thus providing a good substitute for other vegetable oils such as from olive, safflower, and rape seed (Martin, 1979; Girgis and Said, 1968; Kamel and Blackman, 1982). The *L. acutangula* is believed to be native to the old world tropics (Jeffrey, 1980). India is considered as a primary centre of origin (Chakravarty, 1990). Africa is proposed as a second domestication centre (Potterfield, 1955). *L. acutangula* has a pan tropic distribution (Tindall, 1987) between latitudes 40 °C and 30 °C South, but mainly around South East Asia, Africa, and South America (Jeffery, 1980). Unlike other cucurbits, it is adapted to hot humid tropics (Purseglove, 1968; Herklot, 1972). However, the area and production of ridge gourd is 9766.39 ha and 47335 metric tons, respectively (BBS, 2016) in Bangladesh. This vegetable grows well in sandy, fertile soils and requires good sunlight and humid conditions to flourish. One hundred and fifty five accessions, 56 new collections and some previous collections are being conserved at PGRC gene bank of BARI, Gazipur. Out of them 133 accessions had been characterized. Hence, the present study has been designed to study the genetic diversity, to identify useful traits and predict their potentiality for utilization and conservation.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in the experimental field of Plant Genetic Resources Centre (PGRC) of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, during the Rabi season of 2017-18. Although about 80 ridge gourd germplasm were included in the experiment but out of them only 44 germplasm were germinated and among them lastly seeds of 40 collections were

obtained due to seasonal problem. The germplasm were collected from different parts of Bangladesh. The seeds were sown in the well prepared seed beds on last 11 November, 2018 and twenty four days old seedlings were transplanted in the pit of main plot whereas the unit plot size was 3X2 m². The experiment was designed in RCB (Randomized Complete Block) format. Omini and Hossian (1987), working with *L. aegyptica* observed that potassium containing nutrient treatments (Potassium, Nitrogen-Potassium, and Phosphorous-Potassium) promoted staminate flowering while phosphorous and nitrogen containing treatments (Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Nitrogen-Phosphorous, and Nitrogen-Phosphorous-Potassium) promoted femaleness and reduced staminate flowering. These results are consistent with the findings reported for monoecious cucurbits (Hall, 1949; Heslop and Harrison, 1972; Dhaparidze, 1976). That's why recommended fertilizers were applied as 20 ton/ha cow-dung, 175kg/ha Urea, 175 kg/ha TSP, 150kg/ha MP, 100kg/ha Gypsum, 12.5 kg/ha ZnSO₄ and 10 kg/ha Borax stated by Mondal *et al.*, (2011). Moreover, for proper growth and development of the ridge gourd plants, trail was made with bamboo and plastic wire. Picking of matured fruits started from last week of January, 2018 and continued up to February, 2018. Five times weeding and mulching were done at 20 days interval over the experimental period. Over the experimental period some insects and diseases disturbed the plants. To control red pumpkin beetle, mite and leaf miner, Sevin @ 2g/Lit, Vertimec 18 EC @ 1.2 ml/L and Ripcord @ 2 ml/L were applied during seedling and vegetative stage. For controlling leaf blight and root rot disease of ridge gourd, Autostin @ 2g/Lit and Indofil @ 2g/Lit water were applied alternately within 7-10 days interval. Both qualitative and quantitative data were recorded as per IBPGR descriptor (1981) and those data were subjected to statistical analysis adopting 'Analysis of Variance' techniques (Panse and Sukhatme, 1978) using R software to find out the variability among the germplasm.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative characters

Cotyledon size: Among the collection, three different categories of cotyledonous leaf size were found, named as small, medium and large. Observed frequencies of cotyledonous leaf size were significantly different from the frequency of expected number of equal distribution. The expected number of germplasm for an equal distribution was 14.67 (Table 1).

Cotyledon colour: Extend of green color of cotyledonous leaves may vary in different genotypes/variety of crops. Thus dark green, light green and mixture of both were observed in the

collection (Table 1). Observed distribution of frequencies of germplasm palms of Cotyledonous leaf color was statistically different from the expected number of germplasm for an equal distribution (14.67).

Leaf shape: Three shapes of leaf, namely ovate, orbicular and reniform were noticed in the collection. The distribution of genotypes under these three categories was significantly different from the frequency of expected number of equal distribution which was 14.67 (Table 1). The estimated χ^2 value was 8.91 which was higher than its critical value.

Leaf size: As per descriptor three groups of leaf size were recorded namely small, intermediate and large. Distribution of genotypes under these three categories of leaf size was independent as compared to the expected number of their equal distribution 14.67 (Table 1). The collection of genotypes was dominated by the genotypes with intermediate type leaf size.

Leaf margin: All the collected germplasm flourished with dentate type leaf margin (Table 1).

Leaf lobe: The leaves of the germplasm were also differentiated for having different depth of lobes observed as shallow, intermediate and deep. Although the germplasm with intermediate type lobe were dominated in the collection (Table 1) but the distribution of germplasm for each group of leaf lobe was not different statistically from the expected number of equal distribution 14.67. The estimated χ^2 was 1.27 which was lower than its critical value.

Dorsal leaf pubescence: Germplasm were categorized in four classes on the basis of leaf pubescence namely absent, low, intermediate and high (Table 1). The distribution of germplasm for each group of leaf-pubescence was statistically different from the expected number of equal distribution 11.

Ventral leaf pubescence: Three types of ventral leaf pubescence named as low, intermediate and high were noticed in the Germplasm. The distribution of germplasm for each group of leaf-pubescence was statistically different from the expected number of equal distribution 11 (Table 1). The estimated χ^2 was 14.22 which was higher than the critical χ^2 value.

Table 1. Distribution of different characters of leaf from cotyledon to vegetative stage of ridge gourd

Name of Descriptor	Descriptor stage	No of germplasm	Expected No of equal distribution	χ^2 Value	Probability at 5% level of significance
Cotyledon size	Small	1 (2.27 %)	14.67	24.86*	5.99
	Medium	28 (63.64 %)	14.67		
	Large	15 (34.09 %)	14.67		
Cotyledon colour	Dark green	15 (34.09 %)	14.67	21.95*	5.99
	Intermediate	4 (9.09 %)	14.67		
	Light green	25 (56.82 %)	14.67		
Leaf shape	Ovate	10 (22.73%)	14.67	8.91*	5.99
	Orbicular	24 (54.55%)	14.67		
	Reniform	10 (22.73%)	14.67		
Leaf size	Small	2 (4.55%)	14.67	60.58*	5.99
	Intermediate	39 (88.64%)	14.67		
	Large	3 (6.82%)	14.67		
Leaf margin	Dentate	44 (100%)	-	-	-
Leaf lobe	Shallow	12 (27.27%)	14.67	1.27 ^{NS}	5.99
	Intermediate	18 (40.91%)	14.67		
	Deep	14 (31.82%)	14.67		
Dorsal leaf pubescence	Absent	3 (6.82%)	11	49.45*	7.82
	Low	3 (6.82%)	11		
	Intermediate	31 (70.45%)	11		
	High	7 (15.91%)	11		
Ventral leaf pubescence	Low	3 (6.82%)	14.67	14.22*	5.99
	Intermediate	22 (50.00%)	14.67		
	High	19 (43.18%)	14.67		

Growth habit: The plants of all the germplasm showed prostrate type growth habit (Table 2) and that's why for their proper growth and development, bamboo supports were given.

Stem shape: From the cross-sectional view, it was observed that the stem shape was angular which was noticed in all the germplasm (Table 2).

Stem pubescence: As per descriptor, on the presence of stem pubescence, the germplasm were categorized into two groups as thin and dense (Table 2). The distribution of germplasm for each group of stem-pubescence was not different from the expected number of equal distribution statistically. The estimated χ^2 was 2.28 which was smaller than its criticalvalue.

Tendrils: The plants of all the germplasm produced many tendrils to get support for their growth (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of different characters of stem and growth habit of ridge gourd

Name of Descriptor	Descriptor stage	No of germplasm	Expected No of equal distribution	χ^2 Value	Probability at 5% level of significance
Growth habit	Prostate	44(100%)	-	-	-
Stem shape	Angular	44(100%)	-	-	-
Stem pubescence	Thin	17 (38.64%)	22	2.28 ^{NS}	3.84
	Dense	27 (61.36%)	22		
Tendrils	Present	44(100%)	-	-	-

Flower colour : The plants of all the germplasm flashed with light yellow and yellow coloured flowers where yellow colour showed the dominancy but their distribution for each group of was not different from the expected number of equal distribution statistically (Table 3).

Sex type: Though the plants of cucurbitaceae family show different types of sexual attitudes, but here all the plants of different germplasm exposed the same sexual form and that was momoecious (Table 3).

Fruit colour: Light green and green coloured fruits were obtained from the germplasm and their distribution for each group of was different significantly from the expected number of equal distribution 22 (Table 3).

Peduncle shape: It was noticed that the plants of all germplasm had round shape peduncle (Table 3).

Stem-end fruit shape: The stem-end fruit shape of all the plants of germplasm was pointed shape (Table 3).

Blossom end fruit shape: The plants of all the germplasm produced blossom end (Table 3) fruits.

Fruit shape: Among the collection, three different shapes of fruits were found, named as oblong bloky, elliptical and pyriform. The observed frequencies of fruit shape were significantly different from the frequency of expected number of equal distribution. The expected number of germplasm for an equal distribution was 14.22 (Table 3).

Fruit skin texture: The fruits of all the germplasm were categorized into three groups on the basis of skin texture named as shallowly wavy, with warts and scabrous. Distribution of genotypes under these three categories was independent as compared to the expected number of their equal distribution 14.67 (Table 3). The collection of genotypes was dominated by the genotypes having shallowly wavy type skin.

Fruit rib: Fruits with superficial, intermediate and deep ribs were obtained from the germplasm and their distribution for each group was different significantly from the expected number of equal distribution 14.67 (Table 3).

Flesh colour: White and cream colour flesh was obtained from the germplasm and distribution of genotypes under these two categories was independent as compared to the expected number of their equal distribution 22 (Table 3). The collection of genotypes was dominated by the genotypes having cream colour flesh.

Seed surface: The surface of the seed was exposed as smooth and slightly pitted among the germplasm and their distribution for each group was different significantly from the expected number of equal distribution 22 (Table 3).

Seed colour: Four different colours of seeds were found among the collection, visually black, gray, brown and white. The observed frequencies of seed colour were significantly different from the frequency of expected number of equal distribution 66.4 (Table 3).

Table 3. Distribution of different characters of reproductive parts of ridge gourd

Name of Descriptor	Descriptor stage	No of germplasm	Expected No of equal distribution	χ^2 Value	Probability at 5% level of significance
Flower colour	Light yellow	16 (36.36%)	22	3.28 ^{NS}	3.84
	Yellow	28 (63.64%)	22		
Sex type	Monoecious	44 (100%)	-	-	-
Fruit colour	Light green	33 (75%)	22	11*	3.84
	Green	11 (25%)	22		
Peduncle shape	Round	44 (100%)			
Stem-end fruit shape	Pointed	44 (100%)	-	-	-
Blossom end fruit shape	Round	44 (100%)	-	-	-
Fruit shape	Oblong bloky	22 (50%)	14.67	14.22*	5.99
	Elliptical	3 (6.82%)	14.67		
	Pyriform	19 (43.18%)	14.67		
Fruit skin texture	Shallowly wavy	32 (72.73%)	14.67	30.86*	7.82
	With warts	5 (11.36%)	14.67		
	Scabrous	7 (15.91%)	14.67		
Fruit rib	Superficial	13 (29.55%)	14.67	0.59 ^{NS}	5.99
	Intermediate	17 (38.64%)	14.67		
	Deep	14 (31.82%)	14.67		
Flesh colour	White	6 (75%)	22	18.18*	3.84
	Cream	34 (25%)	22		

Seed surface	Smooth	27 (67.5%)	20	4.9*	3.84
	Slightly pitted	13 (32.5%)	20		
Seed colour	Black	32 (80%)	10	66.4*	7.82
	Gray	2 (5%)	10		
	Brown	5 (12.5%)	10		
	White	1 (2.5%)	10		

Quantitative characters

The mean performance of different quantitative characters of 44 germplasm of ridge gourd has been shown in the Table 4. From the table it is clear conscience that all the germplasm responded significantly against different characters. In case of seedling emergence, most of the plants came out within 3.5 to 10 days after sowing but the germplasm BD-10282 took longer period (18.8 days) which was exceptional. The plants of AR-197 collected material grew up with higher internode (22.67 cm) length followed by AR-244 (19.63cm) and AHM-215 (19.49 cm) respectively. The germplasm TT-167 flashed with large sized leaves (length 14.40 cm & breadth 20.10 cm) compared to others. The highest number of primary lateral shoot (13.5) was found in the plants of AMA-244 and the highest thickness of stem was observed in case of AC-338 germplasm (1.52cm) followed by TT-177 (1.23cm), TT-26 (1.23cm), TT-167 (1.22cm) and AHM-215 (1.22cm) respectively. The material BD-10281 performed significantly in case of petiole length (9.175cm) and for peduncle length, the germplasm RAI-296 possessed the top most place (3.36 cm). Highest fruit length and fruit breadth was obtained from AR-197 (31.80cm) and BD-10281 (10.85cm) germplasm respectively. Fruit weight was highest in RAI-296 germplasm (195g) followed by N-6 (191.5g) and AMA-395 (190.0g) respectively. A wider range (13.55 to 204.6 g) laid down in case of 1000 seed weight of germplasm whereas the collected material AR-197 performed the best.

Table 4. Mean performance of different quantitative characters of ridge gourd

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Days to emergence	Internode length (cm)	Stem thickness (cm)	No of primary lateral shoot	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)
1	AHM-215	7.400 ij	19.485 bc	1.220 b	7.5 fgh	8.25 q	11.55 t
2	AC-147	7.450 hij	9.885 t	1.050 b-g	5.0 ijk	12.15 k-n	16.40 j
3	AC-338	7.900 fg	12.615 r	1.520 a	4.5 jk	13.60 b	18.35 def
4	TT-26	10.100 d	12.850 qr	1.235 b	6.5 ghi	12.10 lmn	16.20 jk
5	TT-167	7.205 jk	12.495 r	1.220 b	6.0 hij	14.40 a	20.10 a

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Days to emergence	Internode length (cm)	Stem thickness (cm)	No of primary lateral shoot	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)
6	TT-177	3.900 p	19.575 b	1.225 b	9.5 de	12.45 h-l	15.30 mno
7	ATR-18	8.300 f	19.750 b	0.950 efg	11.5 bc	12.90 b-j	17.80 fgh
8	ATR-35	9.900 d	15.765 hi	1.005 c-g	4.0 k	11.30 o	13.90 q
9	ATR-39	7.950 fg	14.885 lm	1.205 bc	7.5 fgh	12.50 h-l	16.30 j
10	ATR-40	14.900 b	12.030 s	0.950 efg	11.5 bc	12.95 b-j	16.10 jk
11	AMA-140	12.150 c	15.300 jk	1.245 b	8.5 ef	12.95 b-j	17.45 gh
12	AMA-161	9.165 e	14.150 nop	1.140 b-e	9.5 de	13.05 b-i	15.20 no
13	AMA-182	14.850 b	14.225 no	1.055 b-f	5.5 ijk	12.65 f-l	19.50 ab
14	AMA-244	12.100 c	16.150 h	1.060 b-f	13.5 a	13.45 b-e	18.95 bcd
15	AMA-395	9.150 e	13.165 q	1.150 b-e	8.0 efg	9.40 p	12.25 s
16	RAI-296	7.200 jk	13.745 p	0.950 efg	5.0 ijk	12.25 j-m	16.60 ij
17	R-17	7.850 gh	15.985 hi	0.900 fg	8.5 ef	12.85 c-k	17.20 hi
18	M-33	7.830 ghi	13.865 op	1.050 b-g	5.0 ijk	11.00 o	15.60 k-n
19	KI-38	7.900 fg	15.650 ij	0.950 efg	7.5 fgh	13.50 bcd	19.25 bc
20	IAH-319	9.950 d	17.915 d	1.000 d-g	8.5 ef	12.65 f-l	14.95 no
21	AR-197	6.200 n	22.665 a	0.850 g	4.5 jk	13.45 b-e	18.05 efg
22	AR-244	6.900 kl	19.625 b	0.950 efg	6.5 ghi	11.25 o	14.70 op

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Days to emergence	Internode length (cm)	Stem thickness (cm)	No of primary lateral shoot	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)
23	AR-278	7.835 ghi	19.150 c	1.000 d-g	4.5 jk	12.60 g-l	16.45 j
24	N-6	8.800 e	16.900 fg	0.850 g	4.0 k	13.30 b-g	15.95 j-m
25	N-9	5.250 o	14.050 op	1.050 b-g	5.5 ijk	12.45 h-l	17.25 hi
26	N-10	7.125 jkl	14.485 mn	0.850 g	5.0 ijk	13.10 b-h	15.40 lmn
27	N-11	6.750 lm	17.200 efg	0.950 efg	7.5 fgh	12.35 i-m	18.85 bcd
28	RC-20	10.165 d	13.135 q	1.010 c-g	12.5 ab	13.25 b-g	18.10 efg
29	RC-36	6.885 kl	14.085 nop	1.000 d-g	8.5 ef	8.75 pq	11.65 st
30	RC-74	7.165 jkl	17.970 d	0.900 fg	10.5 cd	12.50 h-l	16.20 jk
31	RC-94	10.150 d	15.200 kl	0.900 fg	7.5 fgh	13.55 bc	18.40 def
32	RC-138	8.850 e	14.930 kl	1.000 d-g	4.0 k	11.65 mno	16.05 jkl
33	RC-155	8.800 e	17.085 efg	0.900 fg	11.5 bc	12.85 c-k	19.35 bc
34	TR-14	6.100 n	17.390 e	0.900 fg	13.5 a	12.75 e-l	14.95 no
35	BD-10275	7.835 ghi	13.150 q	1.050 b-g	11.5 bc	12.95 b-j	18.70 cde
36	BD-10277	8.165 fg	17.425 e	0.900 fg	8.5 ef	11.25 o	14.05 pq
37	BD-10279	6.925 kl	17.250 ef	1.155 bcd	6.5 ghi	12.65 f-l	15.95 j-m
38	BD-10280	6.350 mn	15.120 kl	0.950 efg	5.5 ijk	12.80 d-l	16.35 j
39	BD-10281	7.075 jkl	16.800 g	0.850 g	12.5 ab	12.25 j-m	16.30 j

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Days to emergence	Internode length (cm)	Stem thickness (cm)	No of primary lateral shoot	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)
40	BD-10282	18.800 a	8.875 u	1.165 bcd	5.0 ijk	13.35 b-f	15.25 no
41	BD-10284	6.785 klm	11.935 s	0.850 g	4.5 jk	12.30 j-m	19.20 bc
42	BD-10402	10.300 d	16.010 hi	1.065 b-f	6.0 hij	13.40 b-e	19.50 ab
43	BD-10404	7.025 jkl	16.065 h	0.850 g	10.5 cd	11.20 o	13.05 r
44	BD-10405	7.150 jkl	10.150 t	0.950 efg	6.5 ghi	11.45 no	16.05 jkl
Significant level		***	***	***	***	***	***
CV %		2.56	1.32	9.92	10.29	2.82	2.03

Contd.

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Petiole length (cm)	Peduncle length (cm)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	Coll. No.	1000 seed weight (g)
1	AHM-215	4.895 ij	2.60 e-h	24.30 c	5.40 r	128.0 f-i	AHM-215	13.55
2	AC-147	2.95 n	2.89 b-e	13.40 z	5.30 r	61.5 rs	AC-338	65
3	AC-338	3.58 lm	3.08 ab	14.80 y	4.60 u	67.5 p-s	TT-177	112
4	TT-26	6.91 d	2.93 bcd	15.90 uvw	7.35 kl	58.0 s	ATR-18	129.5
5	TT-167	7 d	3.06 ab	22.80 efg	5.35 r	67.5 p-s	ATR-35	159.3
6	TT-177	2.97 n	2.10 lm	22.25 gh	8.40 hij	187.5 ab	ATR-39	138
7	ATR-18	5.435 fgh	2.32 h-m	19.20 opq	4.80 stu	122.5 ghi	ATR-40	81.2
8	ATR-35	5.295 ghi	3.07 ab	25.90 b	6.40 op	117.5 h-k	AMA-140	81.2
9	ATR-39	8.06 b	2.26 i-m	13.75 z	5.10 rst	58.0 s	AMA-182	144.4
10	ATR-40	5.735 efg	2.80 b-f	14.85 y	4.65 tu	64.0 p-s	AMA-244	106.4
11	MA-140	3.01 n	2.54 f-j	16.30 tu	5.35 r	67.5 p-s	RAI-296	104
12	AMA-161	4.775 j	2.09 m	20.80 kl	7.35 kl	121.5 g-j	R-17	133.1

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Petiole length (cm)	Peduncle length (cm)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	Coll. No.	1000 seed weight (g)
13	AMA-182	4 kl	3.02 b	15.25 xy	9.50 cd	72.5 o-s	M-33	124.4
14	AMA-244	5.05 hij	2.28 h-m	15.65 vwx	6.35 opq	75.0 o-r	KI-37	105
15	AMA-395	3.97 kl	2.98 bcd	21.80 hi	10.25 b	190.0 ab	KI-38	124.6
16	RAI-296	4.91 ij	3.36 a	17.35 s	8.35 ij	195.0 a	IAH-319	84
17	R-17	7.58 c	3.11 ab	19.15 pq	5.20 rs	125.0 f-i	AR-197	204.6
18	M-33	7.04 d	2.96 bcd	25.65 b	6.40 op	122.5 ghi	AR-244	128.4
19	KI-38	6.99 d	3.04 ab	21.45 ij	7.65 k	127.5 f-i	AR-278	113
20	IAH-319	4.215 k	2.52 f-k	18.85 qr	3.40 v	87.5 no	N-6	119.8
21	AR-197	5.84 ef	3.08 ab	31.80 a	7.25 klm	176.5 bc	N-9	128
22	AR-244	6.025 e	3.11 ab	19.30 opq	6.50 op	112.5 i-l	N-10	188
23	AR-278	5.92 e	2.21 klm	15.65 vwx	8.20 j	120.0 hij	N-11	127
24	N-6	3.94 kl	3.02 b	22.90 ef	6.15 pq	191.5 ab	RC-20	70
25	N-9	2.92 n	2.66 d-g	20.35 lm	9.35 de	140.0 def	RC-36	103.5
26	N-10	4.935 ij	2.25 j-m	19.65 nop	8.80 ghi	79.5 op	RC-74	84
27	N-11	5.13 hij	2.67 c-g	20.20 mn	8.90 efg	120.5 g-j	RC-94	96
28	RC-20	4.715 j	2.50 f-k	21.30 ijk	6.80 mno	147.5 d	RC-138	131.2
29	RC-36	4.98 ij	2.24 j-m	19.75 no	5.90 q	117.0 h-k	RC-155	105.3
30	RC-74	5.23 hi	2.14 lm	12.20 A	9.35 de	144.0 de	TR-14	77
31	RC-94	3.98 kl	2.28 h-m	12.40 A	7.00 lmn	67.0 p-s	BD-10275	90.8
32	RC-138	5.12 hij	2.14 lm	23.70 d	9.95 bc	168.0 c	BD-10277	93.9
33	RC-155	4.22 k	2.59 e-i	19.25 opq	9.20 defg	186.5 ab	BD-10279	48.3
34	TR-14	5.115 hij	2.25 j-m	22.40 fg	9.30 def	136.0 dg	BD-10280	104.4
35	BD-10275	4.915 ij	2.59 e-i	16.75 t	8.85 fgh	96.5 mn	BD-10281	55
36	BD-10277	6.88 d	2.35 g-m	16.10 uv	9.30 def	103.0 kn	BD-10282	106.8
37	BD-10279	4.925 ij	2.80 b-f	21.20 jk	3.40 v	96.0 mn	BD-10284	140

Sl. No.	Coll. No.	Petiole length (cm)	Peduncle length (cm)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	Coll. No.	1000 seed weight (g)
38	BD-10280	6.135 e	2.91 b-e	15.20 xy	3.30 v	77.5 opq	BD-10402	109.6
39	BD-10281	9.175 a	3.01 b	18.35 r	10.85 a	129.0 e-h	BD-10404	98
40	BD-10282	4.985 ij	3.05 ab	16.80 st	8.75 ghi	106.0 j-m	BD-10405	95.2
41	BD-10284	4.695 j	2.99 bc	12.35 a	3.55 v	66.5 p-s		
42	BD-10402	3.295 mn	2.94 bcd	15.00 y	6.55 nop	99.5 lmn		
43	BD-10404	5.045 hij	2.80 b-f	15.35 wxy	4.60 u	63.0 qrs		
44	BD-10405	4.16 k	2.42 g-l	23.15 de	6.15 pq	104.0 klm		
Significant level		***	***	***	***	***		
CV %		10.29	6.09	1.46	3.29	6.94		32.54

Correlation analysis of different quantitative characters

From the correlation Table 5, it has been noticed that the characters of germplasm were both positively and negatively correlated, such as days to emergence showed positive relation with leaf length, leaf breadth, number of primary lateral shoots, stem thickness, peduncle length and fruit breadth having negative relation with others. Again leaf length exposed opposite relation with internode length, stem thickness, petiole length, fruit length, fruit breadth and fruit weight but positive with the rest characters. Their remained negative relation for leaf breadth with internode length, stem thickness, petiole length, fruit length and fruit weight. There was no relation among the leaf breadth, number of primary lateral

Table 5. Correlation analysis of different quantitative characters of ridge gourd

	Days to emergence	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)	Inter-node length (cm)	No of primary lateral shoot	Stem thickness (cm)	Petiole length (cm)	Peduncle length	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)
Days to emergence		0.21	0.12	-0.39	0.04	0.18	-0.09	0.14	-0.28	0.02	-0.29
Leaf length (cm)			0.78	-0.06	0.04	-0.01	-0.01	0.07	-0.21	-0.06	-0.19
Leaf breadth (cm)				-0.1	0	-0.01	-0.04	0.18	-0.22	0	-0.17
Inter					0.19	-0.26	0.14	-0.22	0.32	0.06	0.38

-node length (cm)												
No of primary lateral shoot						-0.16	0.13	-0.41	-0.15	0.13	0.03	
Stem thickness (cm)							-0.22	0.03	-0.05	-0.17	-0.24	
Petiole length (cm)								0.16	0.08	0.03	-0.11	
Peduncle length									0.09	-0.17	-0.01	
Fruit length (cm)										0.14	0.58	
Fruit breadth (cm)											0.51	
Fruit weight (g)												

shoots and fruit breadth. Internode length was changed negatively with days to emergence, leaf length, leaf breadth, stem thickness and peduncle length but positive with the rest characters. Number of primary lateral shoots was negatively related with stem thickness, peduncle length, and fruit length. Again, there remained positive relation for stem thickness only with days to emergence and peduncle length but opposite with others. Petiole length was changed negatively with days to emergence, leaf length, leaf breadth, stem thickness and fruit weight. Peduncle length responded positively with days to emergence, leaf length, leaf breadth, stem thickness, petiole length and fruit breadth and negative with others. Fruit length was negatively related with days to emergence, leaf length, leaf breadth, number of primary lateral shoots and stem thickness and had positive relation with the rest characters. Fruit breadth had positive relation with days to emergence, internode length, number of primary lateral shoots, petiole length, fruit length and Fruit weight exposing negative relation with others. Fruit weight was negatively related with days to emergence, leaf length, leaf breadth, stem thickness, petiole length and peduncle length and had positive relation with the rest characters.

Conclusion

It has been revealed from the present study that fruit weight of ridge gourd had strong positive relation with fruit length and fruit breadth and regarding all the characters, the TT-177, AR-197, ATR-18, AHM-215, AC-338, TT-167, , AMA-244, KI-38, N-6, RAI-296, AMA-395, AMA-182, TT-26, RC-155, BD-10281 and BD-10282 germplasm were the promising lines for future breeding programs and other research also.

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